

Socio-economic Disparities among Marginalized Society in Haryana

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Scheduled Castes in India have faced systemic social exclusion, occupational segregation and economic deprivation rooted in the caste system. Despite constitutional safeguards and welfare interventions, disparities in education, land ownership and employment continue to persist, particularly in rural Haryana. The present study addresses the problem of understanding the existing socio-economic conditions of Scheduled Castes and the effectiveness of welfare schemes in improving their livelihoods. It specifically examines demographic profile, occupational patterns, landholding status and factors influencing socio-economic conditions. The study was conducted in Sirsa, Fatehabad, and Bhiwani districts with a sample of 240 respondents. The findings reveal that a majority of respondents belong to the 25-40 years age group with low educational attainment and high dependence on labour work. A significant proportion (68.75%) were landless and nearly half earned annual income between ₹1,00,000-2,00,000, reflecting economic vulnerability. Social participation (81.67%) and mass media exposure (78.33%) were found to be low, indicating limited awareness and mobility. Welfare schemes moderately improved living standards (WMS 2.38), though the overall impact remained limited (overall mean score 1.86). Most respondents (72.92%) belonged to low socio-economic status and faced issues such as poor education quality, low wages and inadequate housing. The study suggests strengthening educational access, skill development and employment opportunities along with effective implementation and monitoring of welfare schemes. There is also a need to enhance awareness, social participation and resource accessibility to uplift the socio-economic conditions of Scheduled Castes.

Keywords: Scheduled castes, socio-economic conditions, welfare schemes, sub-caste, occupational status

The caste system has historically constituted a fundamental axis of social stratification in Indian society, shaping patterns of inequality, exclusion and access to resources. Scheduled Castes (SCs), located at the lower end of this hierarchy, have experienced centuries of socio-economic deprivation, occupational marginalization and social discrimination. Despite the constitutional abolition of untouchability and the introduction of affirmative action policies, structural inequalities rooted in caste continue to persist in contemporary India (Beteille, 1991; Deshpande, 2011). The persistence of these inequalities is particularly evident in rural settings, where traditional hierarchies intersect with agrarian structures and limited livelihood opportunities.

In Haryana, a predominantly agrarian state, socio-economic disparities among marginalized communities are closely linked with

unequal land distribution, limited access to education and dependence on low-paid manual labour. Studies have shown that Scheduled Castes in rural North India continue to face restricted social mobility due to entrenched caste relations and unequal access to productive assets (Thorat & Newman, 2012). Although various welfare schemes such as scholarships, housing programmes and livelihood initiatives have been implemented, their effectiveness in transforming the socio-economic conditions of SC households remains a subject of critical inquiry.

Against this backdrop, the present study attempts to analyse the socio-economic conditions of Scheduled Castes in Haryana with a focus on demographic characteristics, occupational structure, landholding patterns and access to welfare schemes. It also seeks to identify the factors influencing socio-economic status and the extent to which welfare interventions have contributed to improving living conditions. The study further highlights critical challenges such as poor quality of education, landlessness, low wage employment and inadequate housing conditions. Statistical analysis reveals that variables such as education, occupation, landholding and income are significantly associated with socio-economic conditions, suggesting that structural factors continue to shape inequality.

In view of findings, the study emphasizes the need for targeted policy interventions focusing on educational advancement, skill development, livelihood diversification and equitable access to resources. Strengthening the implementation of welfare schemes, enhancing awareness and promoting social participation are essential for achieving inclusive and sustainable socio-economic development among Scheduled Castes in Haryana. In light of the above statements, the paper attempts to answer the following research questions:

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Research Questions

- To study the demographic composition among Scheduled Castes in rural community of Haryana
- To delineate the socio-economic and cultural dimensions of caste-based occupations
- To examine the socio-economic impact of schemes on Scheduled Caste families
- To delineate the factors affecting with socio-economic conditions along with constraints

Method

Participants

The study was conducted in three districts of Haryana namely Sirsa, Fatehabad and Bhiwani. A total of 240 Scheduled Caste respondents were selected for the study, with 80 respondents drawn randomly from each district. The respondents were selected from villages such as Ludhesar, Lehra Theh and Rupana (Sirsa); Shakarpura, Kanhari and Samain (Fatehabad); and Dharan and Kharkari Sohan (Bhiwani). The sample represents diverse sub-castes including Chamar, Balmiki, Nayak and Megh communities, ensuring adequate representation of socio-economic variations.

Measure

Data were collected using a well-structured interview schedule developed in accordance with the objectives of the study. The instrument included variables related to demographic characteristics, education, occupation, landholding, income, social participation, mass media exposure and socio-economic status. Additionally, scales were constructed to assess housing conditions, welfare scheme utilization and socio-economic impact using weighted mean scores (WMS), total weighted scores (TWS) and ranking techniques.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were systematically coded, classified and tabulated for analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used to describe the socio-economic profile of respondents. Analytical tools including total weighted score, weighted mean score, rank order and overall mean score were employed to assess the severity and impact of variables. Inferential statistics, particularly the chi-square test, were applied to examine the association between socio-economic variables and overall socio-economic conditions of respondents.

Procedure

The study followed a field-based empirical research design. After selecting the study area and respondents through random sampling, primary data were collected through personal interviews conducted by the researcher. Respondents were approached in their respective villages, and information was gathered in a systematic manner to ensure accuracy and reliability. The collected data were verified, compiled and subjected to statistical analysis to derive meaningful interpretations aligned with the objectives of the study.

Results and Discussion

The results present the age-wise distribution of 240 Scheduled Caste respondents across three districts namely Sirsa, Fatehabad and

Bhiwani with 80 respondents from each district. The more than half of respondents (50.83%) hailed from 2540 years age group and 4055 years group (28.33%), while 20.84 per cent respondents were above 55 years of age group. District-wise, both Sirsa and Bhiwani have the highest proportion of young respondents (55.00%), whereas Fatehabad has a slightly older profile, with 35.00% in 4055 years group and the highest average age of 44.5 years. The overall average age of the respondents across all districts was 43 years. Sub-caste wise data reveals that 39.58 per cent respondents belonged to Chamar community and Balmiki (34.16%). This table 1 presents the distribution of educational attainment among Scheduled Caste respondents across three districts. Nearly one-fourth of respondents (23.75%) were illiterate, while 6.67 per cent have attained graduation or higher education. District-wise analysis reveals that Sirsa has the highest percentage of illiterate respondents (43.75%) and the lowest average education level (5.15). Bhiwani demonstrates better educational outcomes, with the lowest illiteracy rate (7.50%), the highest percentage of graduates (12.5%) and the highest average education level (8.56). The overall average education of the respondents across all districts was 6.72 class. The data indicates that 35.42 per cent respondents were engaged in labour work followed by share cropping occupation (20.41%) and contractual landholders (15.00%). This table outlines the landholding status of Scheduled Caste respondents across the districts. More than two-third of respondents (68.75%) were landless. Contrary to that small percentage of the respondents (15.83%) had marginal land holding followed by small (11.25%) and semi-medium (4.17). Bhiwani reports the highest average landholding (1.64 acres) followed by Sirsa (1.00 acres), while Fatehabad has negligible average of 0.16 acres. The overall average landholding of the respondents across all districts was 0.93 acre.

The data highlights that more than half of the respondents (55.00%) had nuclear family and joint family (45.00%), respectively. More than three-fifth of the respondents (62.50%) had 5-8 members in their family. The data presents the distribution of annual family income among Scheduled Caste respondents across three districts. Further, analysis reveals that nearly half of the respondents (48.75%) earned the income range of Rs. 1,00,000,2,00,000/- indicating low-income levels across the sample. A smaller proportion (15.00%) earned above Rs. 4,00,000/- annually. Region-wise data shows that Sirsa and Fatehabad had the lowest income group (55.00% and 62.5% respectively). Bhiwani shows relatively better income levels, with 27.50% earning above Rs. 4,00,000/- and the highest average annual income of Rs. 3,01,250/-. The overall average income of the respondents across all districts was Rs. 2,49,166/-. Overwhelming majority of the respondents (81.67%) had no social participation in any social organization. Even 10.83 per cent respondents participated in one social organization. It was found that more than three-fourth of the respondents (78.33%) had low level of exposure to mass-media. A perusal of data reveals that nearly three-fourth of the respondents (72.92%) had low level of socio-economic status.

Gender-wise Distribution

Figure 1 presents the gender-wise distribution of 240 Scheduled Caste respondents across four major sub-castes namely Chamar, Balmiki, Nayak and Megh. The sample was male-dominated with 85.00 per cent males and 15.00 per cent females. Sub-caste wise analysis reveals that Chamar was the most represented sub-caste

Figure 1*Gender-wise Distribution of Respondents (n=240)*

among both males (41.18%) and females (30.55%). Balmiki females constituted the highest proportion among female respondents (41.67%), while males account for 32.85%. Megh was the least

represented group in both genders, 8.82 per cent of males and 5.55 per cent of females.

Marital Status and Age Group

A perusal of data in Table 1 reveals a detailed breakdown of the marital status of Scheduled Caste respondents, categorized by gender and age group. Overall marital status highlights that majority of respondents (70.42% males and 4.58% females) were married. Unmarried respondents made up 7.78 per cent of males and 1.66 per cent of females. Widows/widowers represented 5.42 per cent of males and 7.92 per cent of females, while divorced individuals form a small minority 1.66 per cent males and 1.26 per cent females. Age-wise trends reveal that most of the respondents were married (56.21% males, 36.36% females) in 25-40 years age group, but this group also had the highest proportion of unmarried individuals (58.82% males, 50.00% females). Above 55 years age group showed the highest share of widows/widowers (61.55% males, 52.63% females), reflecting age-related spousal loss.

Table 1*Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status and Age Group (n=240)*

Marital status / Age group	Unmarried		Married		Widow/widower		Divorced	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
25-40 yrs.	10(58.82)	2(50.00)	95(56.21)	4(36.36)	2(15.38)	3(15.79)	3(75.00)	3(100)
40-55 yrs.	4(23.52)	1(25.00)	49(29.00)	4(36.36)	3(23.07)	6(31.58)	1(25.00)	0
Above 55 yrs.	3(17.66)	1(25.00)	25(14.79)	3(27.28)	8(61.55)	10(52.63)	0	0
Total	17(07.78)	4(01.66)	169(70.42)	11(04.58)	13(05.42)	19(07.92)	4(01.66)	3(01.26)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage

Educational Status and Age Group

Table 2 illustrates the educational attainment of respondents across different age groups. Regarding age-wise educational trend reveals that 25-40 years age group showed the highest percentage of respondents with education at all levels beyond illiteracy, particularly at the primary (64.70%), middle (52.17%) and graduation (50.00%) levels, reflecting educational improvement in

the younger generation. Above 55 years age group contributed the highest to illiteracy (29.83%) but the least to graduation or above (18.75%), indicating lower access to education in earlier decades. This mirrors national data from the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO, 78th Round, 2021), which reported that SCs consistently lag behind in secondary and tertiary education attainment due to financial constraints, caste-based discrimination and poor access to quality education.

Table 2*Distribution of Respondents by Educational Status and Age Group (n=240)*

Educational status / Age group	Illiterate	Primary school	Middle school	Secondary school	Senior secondary school	Graduation or above
	25-40 yrs.	26(45.61)	33(64.70)	24(52.17)	21(46.67)	10(40.00)
40-55 yrs.	14(24.56)	16(31.37)	12(26.08)	13(28.88)	8(32.00)	5(31.25)
Above 55 yrs.	17(29.83)	2(03.93)	10(21.75)	11(24.45)	7(28.00)	3(18.75)
Total	57 (23.75)	51 (21.25)	46 (19.16)	45 (18.75)	25 (10.42)	16 (6.67)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage

Addiction Habits and Sub-caste

Table 3 presents that three-fourth of the respondents (75.00%) reported some form of addiction. The most common addiction was tobacco use (54.58%) followed by alcoholism (36.25%) and technology addiction (16.25%). Sub-caste-wise data reveals that

Balmiki respondents showed the highest levels of addiction across most categories, especially tobacco (81.70%), alcohol (51.21%) and gambling (20.73%). Chamar respondents had a mixed pattern with 34.74% addicted to tobacco and 22.10% to alcohol. Megh respondents showed the lowest overall addiction levels, with 60.00% reporting no addiction.

Table 3*Distribution of Respondents by Addiction Habits and Sub-caste (n=240)*

Type of addiction / Sub-caste	No addiction	Tobacco addiction	Alcoholism	Technology addiction	Gambling addiction	Drug Abuse
Chamar	25(26.31)	33(34.74)	21(22.10)	16(16.84)	9(9.47)	6(6.31)
Balmiki	8(9.75)	67(81.70)	42(51.21)	14(17.07)	17(20.73)	9(10.94)
Nayak	15(34.88)	23(53.48)	21(48.83)	6(13.95)	8(18.60)	4(9.30)
Megh	12(60.00)	8(40.00)	3(15.00)	3(15.00)	0	0
Total	60(25.00)	131(54.58)	87(36.25)	39(16.25)	34(14.16)	19(7.91)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage. Multiple responses

Dietary Habits and Sub-caste

Figure 2 illustrates that more than two-third of respondents (71.66%) followed the non-vegetarian diet, while only 28.34 per cent were vegetarian. Balmiki (90.25%) and Nayak (88.38%) respondents predominantly consumed non-vegetarian food. Chamar respondents were more evenly divided, with 55.78% non-vegetarian and 44.22% vegetarian. Megh respondents showed the opposite trend with the highest proportion of vegetarians (65.00%).

Figure 2*Distribution of Respondents by Dietary Habits and Sub-caste*

Traditional Work and Sub-caste

A perusal of data reveals that more than three-fourth of respondents (78.35%) have completely moved away from traditional occupations in Figure 3. Only 8.75 per cent are still engaged solely in traditional work, while 12.90 per cent combine traditional with other work. Further, sub-caste-wise Patterns highlights that Chamar community show the highest shift, with 94.75 per cent having changed their traditional occupation. Balmiki and Nayak sub-castes displayed comparatively greater continuity, with 18.30 per cent and 9.30 per cent, respectively.

Figure 3*Distribution of Respondents by Traditional Work and Sub-caste*

Occupational Composition and Sub-caste

It was found in Table 4 that majority of the respondents (60.41%) were engaged in labour work, reflecting the continued dependence on low-paid, manual employment. Other occupations included contractual landholding (26.25%), small-scale enterprises (16.25%) and sharecropping (16.07%). Chamar respondents show more occupational diversity, with notable engagement in government/private jobs (20.00%), contractual landholding (24.21%) and small-scale enterprises (18.94%). Balmiki respondents are overwhelmingly concentrated in labour work (86.58%), with limited presence in formal jobs (8.53%). These results are further corroborated by studies such as that by Shah and Jodhka (2010), which indicate that caste continues to influence access to employment opportunities in rural labour markets. This study also finds that 71.95% have shifted away from traditional caste-based occupations, an encouraging sign of occupational diversification. However, as emphasized by Gupta (2013), such transitions often lead to low-paying informal sector jobs rather than genuine social mobility.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Occupational Composition and Sub-caste (n=240)

Occupation / Sub-caste	Labour croppers	Share	Contractual landholders	Small scale enterprise	Government/private jobs
Chamar	46(48.42)	15(15.78)	23(24.21)	18(18.94)	19(20.00)
Balmiki	71(86.58)	18(21.95)	15(18.30)	12(14.63)	7(8.53)
Nayak	27(62.79)	7(16.27)	8(18.60)	5(11.62)	4(9.30)
Megh	0	0	17(85.00)	4(20.00)	5(25.00)
Total	145(60.41)	40(16.07)	63(26.25)	39(16.25)	35(14.58)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage

Poverty Line Status and Sub-caste

Figure 4 presents that overwhelming majority of the respondents (88.34%) were classified as above the poverty line (APL), while 11.66 per cent hailed below the poverty line (BPL). Further, analysis revealed that Chamar and Megh respondents also fare well with 90.52 per cent and 100 per cent respectively in the APL category. In contrast, Balmiki respondents have the highest proportion below the poverty line (17.08%), indicating relatively greater economic vulnerability within this sub-caste. As noted by Himanshu (2020), the official poverty line often underestimates rural deprivation and many "non-BPL" households still experience multidimensional poverty.

Figure 4

Distribution of Respondents by Poverty Line Status and Sub-caste

Number of Working Members in family

A perusal of data on workforce distribution reveals in Figure 5 that half of all families (50.00%) have two working members. More than one-fourth of the respondents (28.75%) had three or more earners, while 21.25 per cent rely on a single income earner.

Landholding Status and Sub-caste

Figure 6 outlines that nearly two-third of the respondents (68.75%) were landless in the field of the study. Even 15.83 per cent respondents were marginal farmers followed by small (11.25%) and semi-medium (4.17). Further, data showed that overwhelming majority of the respondents in Balmiki and Nayak community were landless, indicating deep-rooted economic marginalization. Chamar community show slightly better access to land, with owning land - either up to 2.5 acres, between 2.5-5.0 acres or 5.0-10.0 acres. The findings of this study are consistent with a growing body of literature

on the socio-economic marginalization of SCs in rural India. The result that 93.33% of SC respondents in Haryana are landless aligns with the national pattern reported by Thorat and Dubey (2012), who found that landlessness among SC households is over 70% in most agrarian states, significantly limiting their economic mobility and agency.

Figure 5

Distribution of Respondents' Families by Number of Working Members

Figure 6

Distribution of Respondents by Landholding Status and Sub-caste

Ownership of Luxury Goods

It was found from the field of the study that cell phones (91.25%) and LPG connections (79.16%) were the most commonly owned items across households. Motorcycles (63.75%), refrigerators (55.83%) and computers/laptops/tablets (41.66%) showed moderate penetration. Chamar respondents also showed relatively strong ownership of motorcycles (76.84%), LPG (87.05%) and refrigerators (61.05%).

Table 5

Distribution of Respondents by Ownership of Luxury Goods-

Luxury goods	Sub-caste					
	Car	Motorcycle	Refrigerator	LPG	Cell phone	Computer/ Laptop/tab
Chamar	6(6.31)	73(76.84)	58(61.05)	77(87.05)	91(36.84)	35(36.84)
Balmiki	2(2.43)	34(41.46)	31(37.80)	59(71.95)	68(82.92)	23(28.04)
Nayak	1(2.32)	26(60.46)	25(58.13)	34(79.06)	40(93.02)	22(51.16)
Megh	3(15.00)	20(100.00)	20(100.00)	20(100.00)	20(100.00)	20(100.00)
Total	12(5.00)	153(63.75)	134(55.83)	190(79.16)	219(91.25)	100(41.66)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, Multiple responses

Table 6*Distribution of Respondents by Housing Status (n=240)*

Housing status	Poor conditions	Average conditions	Good conditions	TWS	WMS	Rank
Poor quality of housing	116(48.34)	65(27.08)	59(24.58)	537	2.24*	I
Overcrowding in their families	105(43.76)	58(24.16)	77(32.08)	508	2.12*	II
Lack of basic amenities	99(41.25)	66(27.50)	75(31.25)	504	2.10*	III
Lack of durable housing	88(36.67)	79(32.91)	73(30.42)	495	2.06*	IV
Poor construction materials	92(38.34)	70(29.16)	78(32.50)	494	2.05*	V
Lacking proper ventilation	81(33.75)	85(35.41)	74(30.83)	487	2.03	VI
Availability of separate room for family members	55(22.91)	62(21.67)	123(51.25)	392	1.71	VII
Overall Mean Score: 2.04						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Welfare Schemes Aailed by Respondents

Table 7 outlines that majority of the respondents (66.25%) availed the Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme, indicating a relatively strong

focus on educational support. Even 21.67 per cent respondents availed Residential Plot Scheme followed Old Age Pension Scheme (19.58%) and Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (18.75%).

Table 7*Welfare Schemes Aailed by Respondents (n=240)*

Welfare schemes	Frequency	Percentage
Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme	159	66.25
Residential Plot Scheme	52	21.67
Old Age Pension Scheme	47	19.58
Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana	45	18.75
Financial Assistance for Self-Employment	39	16.25
Healthcare/Aayushman Schemes	32	13.34
Dr. Ambedkar Awas Navinikaran Yojana	31	12.91
Vocational Training and Skill Development Schemes	23	09.58
Dr. Ambedkar Medhavi Chhattar Sanshodhit Yojna	15	06.25
Widow pension Scheme	19	07.91

Note. Multiple responses

Socio-economic Impact of Welfare Schemes on Respondents' Families

A perusal of data reveals that more than half of the respondents (56.25%) agreed that welfare schemes have helped in improving their standard of living through poverty alleviation, which ranked

first with the highest weighted mean score (WMS) of 2.38. The impact on housing and infrastructure was viewed positively by 31.67%, though 35.42% disagreed, placing it second (WMS: 1.96). The overall mean score is 1.86, indicating a moderate to low perceived impact of welfare schemes.

Table 8*Socio-economic Impact of Welfare Schemes on Respondents' Families (n=240)*

Impact of welfare schemes	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	TWS	WMS	Rank
Improved standard of living through poverty alleviation programme	135(56.25)	61(25.41)	44(18.34)	571	2.38*	I
Improved their living conditions by housing and infrastructure	76(31.67)	79(32.91)	85(35.42)	471	1.96*	II
Empowered through access to education	46(19.16)	96(40.00)	98(40.83)	428	1.78	III
Increased income through skill development and employment	25(10.41)	116(48.34)	99(41.25)	406	1.69	IV
Enhanced well-being of family by healthcare services	32(13.34)	101(42.08)	107(44.58)	405	1.68	V
Reduced disparities through various welfare schemes	23(09.58)	115(47.92)	102(42.50)	401	1.67	VI
Overall Mean Score: 1.86						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Overall Socio-economic Conditions

Figure 7 highlights the distribution of Scheduled Caste respondents based on various parameters of their overall score was calculated regarding socio-economic conditions. It was found that nearly two-fifth of Scheduled Caste respondents (38.75%) were living in average socio-economic conditions, while 35.42% in poor conditions. Only 25.83 per cent respondents hailed into good socio-economic conditions category.

Figure 7

Level of Socio-economic Conditions of Scheduled Caste Respondents (n=240)

Socio-Economic Conditions of Scheduled Caste Respondents (n=240)

Socio-economic Variables and Socio-economic Conditions

Table 9 presents that various socio-economic variable associated with socio-economic conditions. On the other hand, Types of family, size of family and social participation were not significantly associated with socio-economic conditions of respondents. Age of the respondents was found significantly associated with socio-economic conditions. Further, analysis reveals that maximum number of the respondents (45.90%) belonged to 25-40 years age group had average socio-economic conditions. Contrary to that 36.00 per cent respondents belonged above 55 years age group had poor socio-economic conditions. Sub-caste of the respondents was found highly significantly associated with socio-economic

conditions. Further, analysis reveals that more than half of the respondents (52.44%) belonged to Balmiki community had average socio-economic conditions. In comparison, 45.00 per cent respondents belonged to Megh community had good socio-economic conditions. Education of the respondents was found highly significantly associated with socio-economic conditions. It was also found that maximum number of the respondents (43.75%) educated up to graduation or above had good socio-economic conditions. Contrary to that 50.88 per cent respondents who were illiterate had poor socio-economic conditions. Occupation of the respondents was found highly significantly associated with socio-economic conditions. It was also found that more than half of the respondents (52.00%) engaged in any two types of occupation had good socio-economic conditions. Contrary to that 65.88 per cent respondents engaged in labour work had poor socio-economic conditions.

Highly Significant association was found between landholding and socio-economic conditions. Analysis shows that nearly three-fourth of the respondents (70.00%) related to semi-medium landholding had good socio-economic conditions. On the other hand, maximum number of the respondents (47.27%) who were landless had poor socio-economic conditions. Highly significant association was found between annual family income and socio-economic conditions. Further, analysis explores that nearly three-fifth of the respondents (58.14%) who earned Rs. 3,00,000 to 4,00,000/- had good socio-economic conditions. On the other hand, maximum number of the respondents (41.88%) who earned Rs. 1,00,000 - 2,00,000/- had poor socio-economic conditions. Mass-media exposure was found highly significantly associated with socio-economic conditions. Table 9 presents that more than half of the respondents (51.85%) related to high mass-media exposure had good socio-economic conditions. Contrary to that 39.13 per cent respondents related to low mass-media exposure had poor socio-economic conditions. Socio-economic status was also found highly significantly associated with socio-economic conditions. Further, results highlight that more than half of the respondents (51.28%) belonged to medium level of socio-economic status had good socio-economic conditions. On the other hand, more than two-fifth of the respondents (40.57%) belonged to low socio-economic status had poor socio-economic conditions.

Table 9

Association between Socio-economic Variables and Socio-economic Conditions (n=240)

Socio-economic variables	Level of socio-economic conditions			Total
	Poor	Average	Good	
Age group 25-40 years	44 (36.07)	56 (45.90)	22 (18.03)	122 (50.83)
40-55 years	23 (33.82)	20 (26.41)	25 (36.76)	68 (28.33)
Above 55 years	18 (36.00)	17 (34.00)	15 (30.00)	50 (20.83)
Total	85 (35.42)	93 (38.75)	62 (25.83)	240 (100.00)
				χ^2 Cal=9.85*
Sub-caste				
Chamar	32(33.68)	32 (33.68)	31(32.64)	95 (39.58)
Balmiki	30 (36.58)	43 (52.44)	9 (10.98)	82 (34.17)
Nayak	16 (37.21)	14 (32.56)	13 (30.23)	43 (17.92)
Megh	7(35.00)	4 (20.00)	9(45.00)	20 (8.33)
				χ^2 Cal=30.012**
Level of education				
Illiterate	29 (50.88)	25 (43.86)	3 (5.26)	57 (23.75)

Illiterate	29 (50.88)	25 (43.86)	3 (5.26)	57 (23.75)
Primary School	20 (39.22)	26 (50.98)	5 (9.80)	51 (21.25)
Middle School	14 (30.43)	12 (26.09)	20 (43.48)	46 (19.17)
Secondary School	12 (26.67)	16 (35.56)	17 (37.78)	45 (18.75)
Senior secondary School	7 (28.00)	8 (32.00)	10 (40.00)	25 (10.42)
Graduation or above	3 (18.75)	6 (37.50)	7 (43.75)	16 (6.67)
				χ^2 Cal=38.04**
Occupation				
Labour	56 (65.88)	21 (24.71)	8 (9.41)	85 (35.42)
Share croppers	7 (14.29)	31 (63.27)	11 (22.45)	49 (20.42)
Contractual land holders	7 (19.44)	21 (58.33)	8 (22.22)	36 (15.00)
Small scale enterprise	4 (22.22)	5 (27.78)	9 (50.00)	18 (7.50)
Government or private jobs	6 (22.22)	8 (29.63)	13 (48.15)	27 (11.25)
Any two of above	5 (20.00)	7 (28.00)	13 (52.00)	25 (10.42)
				χ^2 Cal=77.48**
Size of land holding				
Landless (0)	78(47.27)	59(35.76)	28(16.97)	165 (68.75)
Marginal (Up to 2.5)	5(13.16)	20(52.63)	13(34.21)	38 (15.83)
Small (2.5 - 5.0)	2(7.41)	11(40.74)	14(51.85)	27 (11.25)
Semi-medium (5.0 - 10.0)	0	3(30.00)	7(70.00)	10 (4.17)
				χ^2 Cal= 44.028**
Types of family				
Nuclear	49(37.12)	43(32.57)	40(30.30)	132 (55.00)
Joint	36(33.33)	50(46.30)	22(20.37)	108 (45.00)
				χ^2 Cal= 6.637
Size of family				
Up to 4 members	13(30.23)	14(32.56)	16(37.21)	43 (17.92)
5-8 members	56(37.33)	64(42.67)	30(20.00)	150 (62.50)
Above 8 members	16(34.04)	15(31.92)	16(34.04)	47 (19.58)
				χ^2 Cal=12.036
Annual family income (Rs.)				
1,00,000-2,00,000/-	49 (41.88)	61 (52.14)	7 (5.98)	117 (48.75)
2,00,000-3,00,000/-	21 (47.73)	13 (29.55)	10 (22.73)	44 (18.33)
3,00,000-4,00,000/-	8 (18.60)	10 (23.26)	25 (58.14)	43 (17.92)
Above 4,00,000/-	7 (19.44)	9 (25.00)	20 (55.56)	36 (15.00)
				χ^2 Cal=67.77**
Social participation				
No participation	74 (37.76)	75 (38.27)	47 (23.98)	196 (81.67)
Member of one organisation	7 (26.92)	13 (50.00)	6 (23.08)	26 (10.83)
Member of more than one organisation	4 (22.22)	5 (27.78)	9 (50.00)	18 (7.50)
				χ^2 Cal=7.54
Mass media exposure				
Low (up to 6)	72 (39.13)	77 (41.85)	35 (19.02)	184 (76.67)
Medium (6-12)	7 (24.14)	9 (31.03)	13 (44.83)	29 (12.08)
High (12-18)	6 (22.22)	7 (25.93)	14 (51.85)	27 (11.25)
				χ^2 Cal=19.56**
Socio-economic status				
Low (6-12)	71 (40.57)	75 (42.86)	29 (16.57)	175 (72.92)
Medium (12-18)	9 (23.08)	10 (25.64)	20 (51.28)	39 (16.25)
High (18-24)	5 (19.23)	8 (30.77)	13 (50.00)	26 (10.83)
				χ^2 Cal=29.29**

Note: Figures in parentheses denote percentage, * Significant at 5% level of significance, ** Highly significant at 1% level of significance

Socio-economic Problems Faced by Scheduled Caste Respondents

It was found from the field of the study that most critical problem

identified was the poor quality of education (WMS: 2.35), with 56.25% rating it as very serious, followed by low literacy rates (WMS: 2.34), marked very serious by 54.16% of respondents. Indebtedness and sanitation and drinking water facilities were also

seen as significant but slightly lower in perceived severity (WMS: 2.12 & 2.09 respectively). The overall mean score of 2.11 indicates that respondents face a broad range of moderately to highly serious

socio-economic issues especially in the areas of education, employment and land.

Table 10

Socio-economic Problems Faced by Respondents (n=240)

Socio-economic problems	Very Serious	Serious	Somewhat Serious	TWS	WMS	Rank
Quality of education	135(56.25)	55(22.91)	50(20.84)	565	2.35*	I
Low literacy rates	130(54.16)	62(25.83)	48(20.00)	562	2.34*	II
Landlessness and marginal landholdings	123(51.25)	66(27.50)	51(21.25)	552	2.30*	III
Low wage employment	115(47.91)	72(30.00)	53(22.09)	542	2.26*	IV
Poor housing quality	112(46.67)	68(28.33)	60(25.00)	532	2.22*	V
Limited health services	92(38.34)	101(42.08)	47(19.58)	525	2.19*	VI
Indebtedness	101(42.08)	67(27.91)	72(30.00)	509	2.12*	VII
Sanitation and drinking water facility	103(42.91)	57(23.75)	80(33.34)	503	2.09	VIII
Untouchability	27(11.25)	99(41.25)	114(47.50)	393	1.64	IX
Segregation of habitation	45(18.75)	59(24.58)	136(56.67)	389	1.62	X
Overall Mean Score: 2.11						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Overall, the findings reveal that socio-economic challenges are predominantly severe, with education and literacy emerging as the most critical concerns among respondents. The moderately high mean score further indicates that issues such as indebtedness and basic amenities collectively contribute to persistent structural vulnerabilities.

Conclusion

The present study highlights that socio-economic disparities among Scheduled Castes in Haryana are deeply rooted in structural inequalities shaped by caste, occupation and access to resources. Despite various policy initiatives and welfare programmes, the transformation in their socio-economic conditions remains uneven and limited. From a sociological perspective, the study reaffirms that caste-based marginalization is not merely an economic issue but a multidimensional phenomenon involving social, cultural and structural barriers. Therefore, addressing these disparities requires a holistic and inclusive approach. It is imperative to strengthen educational opportunities, promote skill development and ensure equitable access to land and livelihood resources. Additionally, effective implementation, monitoring and awareness of welfare schemes should be prioritized to enhance their outreach and impact.

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